
UTILIZATION OF WASTE TILES IN STABILIZATION OF BLACK COTTON CLAY BRICKS

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ABSTRACT

Bricks are one of the most widely used materials in building construction; however, the increasing demand for building materials and the growing volume of construction and demolition waste have prompted the search for alternative, sustainable materials. Utilizing industrial waste, particularly in the production of sand bricks, presents a significant opportunity for enhancing sustainability in the construction sector. In this context, waste tiles, which are commonly discarded with minimal economic value, have gained attention as a potential additive for stabilizing clay bricks, which typically exhibit high expansion and contraction. This study explores the use of ground waste tile powder as an additive to black cotton soil to produce stabilized brick specimens. The waste tiles were collected, ground into powder using a Loss Angelis grinder, and sieved through a 75-micron BS sieve. The soil was then mixed with the waste tile powder at 5%, 10%, and 15% replacement levels, and bricks of 215 x 103 x 80 mm dimensions were cast for experimentation. Laboratory investigations were conducted to characterize the black cotton soil in terms of sieve analysis, Atterberg limits, water absorption, specific gravity, compaction, California Bearing Ratio (CBR), and shear strength tests, both for stabilized and non-stabilized soils. The results of the compressive strength tests indicated that the addition of waste tile powder significantly enhanced the compressive strength of the bricks. The compressive strength increased with the percentage of waste tile powder, with the highest increase observed at 15% addition (3.17 N/mm²) compared to the control (0%) with a compressive strength of 2.79 N/mm² at 21 days of air curing. The study concludes that waste tiles, when used as an additive in the production of stabilized black cotton clay bricks, offer significant improvements in strength and have the potential to contribute to sustainable practices in the civil and construction industries.

Key words: Bricks, waste tiles, Black Cotton Soil, Atterberg Limit, Compaction, Water Absorption, Compressive Strength

INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth in population, especially in developing countries like Nigeria, has led to a significant increase in the demand for new building structures. However, this demand is challenged by the rising cost of conventional construction materials. In many developing nations, the construction sector heavily relies on materials such as cement and sand to produce bricks and mortar (Sasah and Kankam, 2017). Unfortunately, the cement industry is a major contributor to global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, responsible for approximately 8% of all anthropogenic greenhouse gases that accelerate climate change (Fraaij & Kentgens, 2008). In light of these environmental concerns, there is growing pressure to find sustainable alternatives that reduce dependence on traditional materials and mitigate the environmental impact of the construction industry.

Moreover, the escalating cost of conventional materials has made them inaccessible to large segments of the population, especially in rural areas. In Nigeria, for example, many individuals cannot afford these materials, making it imperative to explore more affordable and locally sourced alternatives (Mansary & Ghali, 2017). Clay bricks, known for their low cost and effectiveness, have been widely adopted for building homes and infrastructure, especially in rural and semi-urban areas.

The principle of sustainability in construction encourages the use of supplementary materials such as natural aggregates, cementing agents, and additives that can improve the properties of traditional building materials while reducing environmental impact. The use of these materials not only promotes eco-friendly construction but also helps to lower the overall cost of construction (Samadi & Hussein, 2015). Traditionally, bricks were made from clay, a material that has been in use for thousands of years due to its durability, ease of production, and low cost. Bricks are typically rectangular units that can be made from various materials, including shale, clay-bearing soils, concrete, and other soil mixtures, and are bound together by mortar, interlocking, or adhesives to form walls, pavements, and other structural components.

Clay is a natural material composed of very fine mineral fragments, which give it its plasticity when wet. This plasticity allows the material to be molded into different shapes. Upon firing at high temperatures, these mineral fragments become responsible for the strength and durability of the final product (Monterio, Mauricio & Vieira, 2004). To improve the properties of certain soils for construction, a process known as soil stabilization is employed. Soil stabilization involves blending or mixing materials with soil to enhance specific soil characteristics, such as its strength, plasticity, and resistance to water-induced damage. Stabilization can be achieved through various means, including the use of chemical stabilizers such as lime, cement, fly ash, and other waste products (Firoozi, Taha & Khan, 2014; Amin, 2012).

Black cotton soil, which is widely found in regions such as Nigeria, India, South Africa, and parts of the United States, is a problematic soil due to its expansive nature. It tends to swell significantly during the rainy season and shrink drastically during the dry season, causing instability and cracking of structures built on it (Tomlinson, 1999; Osinubi, Soni & Ijimdiya, 2010). Black cotton soil typically has a high clay content (often more than 50%) and is dominated by the mineral montmorillonite, which is known for its large volume changes in response to moisture fluctuations. These characteristics make black cotton soil unsuitable for construction unless treated or stabilized (Ola, 1978; Plait, 1953). However, with proper stabilization, this soil can be made more suitable for use in construction, reducing its expansive tendencies and enhancing its strength (Balogun, 1991; Osinubi et al., 2010).

Traditional methods of stabilizing black cotton soil typically involve adding stabilizing agents like cement, lime, or bitumen, which help mitigate the soil's tendency to expand and contract with moisture variations. However, non-traditional stabilization techniques using materials like polymers, tree resins, and silicates have also shown promise in improving the properties of expansive soils (Newman and Tingle, 2004). The use of waste materials, such as those derived from the construction industry, presents an opportunity to both address environmental issues and enhance the properties of construction materials.

One such material is waste ceramic tiles, which are often discarded at construction sites and in landfills. These waste tiles, which are not typically recycled, pose environmental challenges as they contribute to landfills that take up valuable space and release harmful substances into the environment (Naveen & Antil, 2016). Despite this, studies have shown that ceramic waste can be used effectively in the construction industry, particularly as a fine aggregate in cement and mortar, to improve compressive strength and durability (Jimenez, 2013; Huang, 2012). Ceramic waste has been found to offer benefits such as increased resistance to physical and chemical degradation, making it an attractive option for enhancing the performance of construction materials.

Despite these advantages in other areas of construction, there is limited research on the potential use of waste tiles for stabilizing black cotton clay bricks. This gap in knowledge is the focus of the present study, which aims to investigate the feasibility of incorporating waste ceramic tiles as a stabilizing agent in black cotton soil for brick production. The objective of this research is to assess the effect of adding waste tile powder on the mechanical properties, such as compressive strength and durability, of black cotton clay bricks, with the goal of producing a more sustainable and cost-effective construction material for the building industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Black Cotton Soil

The black cotton soil used in this study was collected from the Gulani Local Government Area of Yobe State, located in the northeastern part of Nigeria, at a latitude of 11° 0' N and a longitude of 11.43° 0' E. Figure 1 shows the location of the soil sample collection site.

The collected soil was air-dried, pulverized manually to break up any clumps, and sieved through a 2.36 mm mesh to remove larger particles. The particle size distribution of the black cotton soil, as shown in Figure 2, indicates that the soil falls under the A-7-6 classification in the AASHTO system, and is categorized as CL and CH in the Unified Soil Classification System. Ola, (2007) reported similar findings. The key physical properties of the black cotton soil are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Physical properties of black cotton soil

Property	Value
Liquid limit (%)	33
Plastic limit (%)	22
Plasticity index (%)	12
Specific gravity	2.01
Maximum dry density (g/cm ³)	1.98
Optimum moisture content (%)	7.4

Fig. 1: Soil Sample Collection

2.2 Waste tiles

Waste tiles are typically generated as by-products in the ceramic industry during the final polishing stages and are also produced during tile installation in buildings. These discarded tiles, often considered waste, were collected and reused for this study. The waste tiles used in this project were sourced from a construction site in the northeastern part of Nigeria.

The collected tiles were broken into smaller pieces and then ground into a fine powder using a Los Angeles machine. The resulting powder was sieved through a 150 μm BS sieve, as shown in Figure 3, to obtain the desired particle size distribution.

The physical properties of the waste tiles, as determined through testing, were found to be as follows: specific gravity = 3.10, relative density = 1.36 g/cm^3 , and a water absorption rate of 15%. The chemical composition of the waste tiles is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Chemical composition of Waste tiles

Chemical composition (%)	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	LOI
Waste tiles	72.5	15.8	3.68	2.03	2.80	0.46	0.2

3.0 Laboratory test

A series of laboratory tests were conducted to evaluate the index and engineering properties of black cotton soil and its stabilization with different percentages of waste tile powder. The tests included index property determination, compaction characteristics, California Bearing Ratio (CBR), and shear strength, aimed at identifying the optimal percentage of waste tile for stabilization.

3.1 Index Properties

The index properties of the black cotton soil were determined through Atterberg Limit tests, which include the liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index. These tests were performed on both untreated black cotton soil and samples stabilized with waste tile powder at 5%, 10%, and 15%. The Atterberg limits were determined in accordance with the guidelines set by British Standard BS 1377 - 2 (1990). This testing method is used to assess the soil's plasticity characteristics, which play a critical role in understanding its behavior when subjected to moisture variations.

3.2 Compaction Test

Compaction tests were conducted on both untreated and stabilized black cotton soil to determine the optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD). A British Standard Light (BSL) compaction apparatus with a mould diameter of 110 mm was used. The soil samples were thoroughly mixed with varying amounts of water and compacted in three equal layers, with each layer receiving 24 blows from a hammer weighing 2.5 kg and dropping from a height of 304.8 mm. This procedure is in accordance with the British Standard for compaction tests and helps determine the density and workability of the soil at different moisture levels, as well as the effect of waste tile powder on these properties.

3.3 California Bearing Ratio (CBR) Test

The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test was performed to assess the strength of the soil and its suitability for use in pavements and road construction. In this test, the resistance of the soil

to penetration by a standard plunger is measured, which provides an indication of the soil's load-bearing capacity. Samples of black cotton soil stabilized with varying percentages (5%, 10%, and 15%) of waste tile powder were tested to determine the effect of stabilization on the soil's strength. The CBR tests were conducted following the procedures outlined in British Standard BS 1377 - 4 (1990), as shown in Figure 4. This test provides valuable insight into the improvement in the soil's load-bearing ability after stabilization with waste tiles.

Fig. 2: California Bearing Ratio Test Apparatus

3.4 Shear Strength test

The shear strength of the soil specimens was evaluated using a shear box apparatus. Each specimen, with a plain grid plate at both the top and bottom, was positioned in the shear box housing and placed on the load frame as shown in Figure 5. The required normal stress was applied, and the rate of longitudinal displacement (shear stress) was adjusted to ensure no drainage occurred during the test.

The upper part of the shear box was slightly raised, creating a gap of approximately 1 mm between the two sections. The test was conducted by applying a horizontal shear load to the specimen until failure occurred or until a 20% longitudinal displacement was reached, whichever came first. To ensure repeatability, the test was conducted on identical specimens under different loading conditions (50 kg, 100 kg, and 150 kg weights), with a time interval of 0.5 minutes between each load application. This procedure allowed for the determination of the shear strength of both untreated and stabilized soil specimens.

Fig. 3: Set up of Shear Strength Test

3.5 Water Absorption Test

The water absorption test was performed to assess the effect of water on the clay bricks. Three different samples of stabilized clay bricks were tested to determine their rate of water absorption over a one-hour period, as shown in Figure 6. Each sample was weighed before immersion in water, and the rate of water absorption was measured after one hour. This test provides valuable information regarding the bricks' porosity and resistance to water infiltration, which is essential for understanding their durability and performance in different environmental conditions.

Fig. 4: Water Absorption Test

3.6 Preparation of Bricks

The clay bricks were produced by manually mixing the black cotton soil with water in proportions based on the plastic and liquid limits of the soil, with slight adjustments made to achieve the desired consistency. The mixing process, shown in Figure 7, ensured uniform distribution of moisture throughout the soil.

Waste tile powder was added to the mixture at varying percentages of 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% to assess its effect on the properties of the stabilized bricks. The water-to-soil ratio was adjusted according to the liquid limit of the black cotton soil, resulting in the following proportions: 22.5%, 25%, 27%, and 28% water content, respectively.

The prepared mixture was then poured into brick molds with dimensions of 215 mm × 103 mm × 80 mm. After molding, the bricks were left to air-cure for a specific duration, during which the stabilization effect of the waste tiles improved the bricks' mechanical properties and durability.

Fig. 5: Production of Brick specimens

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Effects of Waste Tiles on Index properties on Black Cotton Soil

Figure 8 shows the results of the index properties of black cotton soil stabilized with waste tiles at 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15%. The liquid limit increased with the addition of waste tiles. Specifically, the liquid limit rose from 33% for untreated black cotton soil to 36% at 10% waste tile content, before decreasing slightly to 34% at 15%. This initial increase can be attributed to the pozzolanic reaction of waste tiles, which requires more water for hydration. However, the decrease at 15% waste tile addition may be due to flocculation and agglomeration of clay particles, which reduces water retention. These trends align with findings by Akshaya (2012), who reported similar increases and decreases in liquid limit when ceramic dust was added to expansive soils.

The plastic limit of black cotton soil also increased with the addition of waste tiles, from 22% in the untreated soil to a peak of 34% at 5% waste tiles. Beyond this, the plastic limit decreased, reaching 29% at 15% waste tiles. This trend is consistent with the work of Gerald and Shahriar (2000), who observed that while the liquid limit can either increase or decrease, the plastic limit generally increases with the introduction of stabilizing agents. Rakhil and Devi (2016) reported similar findings when waste ceramic dust was added to expansive soils.

Fig. 6: Atterberg Limit results of stabilized black cotton soil

4.2 Results of Shear Strength for Stabilized black cotton soil

The shear strength test results for stabilized and un-stabilized black cotton clay soil, obtained through direct shear testing, are presented in Table 3. The results indicate that the soil's cohesiveness (C) was zero for all percentages of waste tile addition. However, the internal friction angle (ϕ) was significantly enhanced with the addition of waste tiles.

In general, the internal angle of friction (ϕ) of the black cotton soil increased with the addition of waste tiles, particularly at the 10% and 15% replacement levels compared to the un-stabilized soil. This improvement in the internal friction angle suggests that the addition of

waste tiles up to 15% enhances the shear strength of the stabilized soil, indicating a higher quality of stabilization.

Similar findings were reported by Kapil and Ameta (2016), who studied the stabilization of fine sand with ceramic tile waste as an admixture in embankment construction. They found significant improvements in the engineering properties of the sand, including an increase in the angle of internal friction as the quantity of waste ceramic tiles increased. Venkatesh, Heera, and Rakesh (2018) also observed significant improvements in the strength properties of black cotton soil when stabilized with calcium carbide residue. Similarly, Anand and Vageesh (2017) reported an increase in both the angle of internal friction (ϕ) and the cohesion (C) values when varying concentrations of plastic waste were added to the soil.

Table 3: Results of cohesion, angle of internal friction and shear strength of the stabilized black cotton soil.

Percentage Addition of waste tiles (%)	Cohesion (kN/m ²)	Angle of internal Friction (ϕ)	Shear strength (kN/m ²)
0	5	22	45.40
5	0	22	40.40
10	0	35	46.63
15	0	30	57.74

4.3 Results of Compaction test

The results of the Maximum Dry Density (MDD) and Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) from the compaction tests for both treated and untreated black cotton soil are presented in Table 4. The addition of waste tiles led to an increase in the OMC of the stabilized black cotton soil, with slight fluctuations in MDD across the different percentages of waste tile addition.

The increase in OMC can be attributed to a reduction in the amount of free silt and clay, which lowers the surface area of the soil particles, thereby reducing the water required for compaction. However, the MDD showed a decrease at the 5% waste tile addition, followed by an increase at 10% and 15% waste tile content. This behavior could be due to changes in particle size and the formation of clusters as a result of the flocculation-agglomeration process, which alters the texture of the soil. These changes in particle structure likely reduced the void ratio, leading to an irregular increase in MDD and a corresponding increase in moisture content for the soil mixture.

Table 4: Results of compaction test for treated and untreated stabilized black cotton soil.

Percentage Addition of waste tiles (%)	MDD (g/cn ³)	OMC (%)
0	1.98	7.4
5	1.77	10.0
10	2.20	12.2
15	2.51	17.8

4.4 California bearing ratio test results

The results of the Un-soaked and Soaked CBR tests for the stabilization of black cotton soil with varying percentages of waste tiles are presented in Table 5. It was observed that the Un-soaked CBR values were higher than the soaked CBR values at both 5% and 10% waste tile additions. At 15% waste tile content, both the soaked and un-soaked CBR values remained constant, with the soaked CBR being slightly higher than the un-soaked at 10%.

This variation can be attributed to the chemical and cementation effects induced by the waste tiles, which may have altered the structural composition of the black cotton soil. In general, the results indicated that the soaked CBR was higher than the un-soaked CBR at both 0% and 10% waste tile additions. However, at 5% stabilization, the un-soaked CBR value was greater than all soaked CBR values.

The study shows that up to 15% waste tile addition had minimal or no significant effect on the stabilization of the black cotton soil bricks, suggesting that higher percentages of waste tiles might not yield further improvements in CBR performance.

Table 5: Results of soak and un-soak CBR at different percent of CKD and OPC Stabilization

Percent (%)	Soak	Un-soak	
	MDD	MDD	OMC
0	9.06	8.01	9.06
5	9.06	10.6	9.82
10	9.82	9.44	7.55
15	9.06	9.06	9.1

4.5 Compressive Strength of black cotton clay Bricks

Figure 9 illustrates the average compressive strength of black cotton clay bricks at 7 days of curing. The compressive strength at the control level (0% waste tiles) was 2.63 MPa. At 5% waste tile replacement, the compressive strength decreased to 2.09 MPa. However, the highest compressive strength of 3.40 MPa was achieved at 15% waste tile addition.

The results further show that at 14 days of curing, the compressive strength of the bricks increased with the addition of waste tiles. For example, the compressive strength at 0% waste tile content increased from 2.63 MPa to 2.79 MPa. This indicates a progressive improvement in the compressive strength of the bricks as the percentage of waste tile powder was increased, particularly at higher levels of waste tile incorporation.

Fig. 7: Results compressive strength of brick specimens

4.9 Water Absorption Test

Figure 10 presents the results of the water absorption test, showing the time duration for which the bricks resisted water before dissolution. The results indicate that the brick specimens containing 15% waste tile powder exhibited the highest resistance to water absorption, with a dissolution time of 19.15 minutes. In contrast, the control specimens (0% waste tiles) had the lowest resistance, with a dissolution time of 7.40 minutes.

Fig. 8: Time taken for the bricks to dissolve in water

5.0 Conclusions

Based on the experimental investigations and the results obtained, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The addition of waste tiles led to an increase in the liquid limit of black cotton soil. Specifically, a 5% addition resulted in a 5.7% increase, while a 15% addition caused a 2.9% increase.
2. The Maximum Dry Density (MDD) of black cotton soil decreased at 5% waste tile addition, but it increased by 10% and 21% at 10% and 15% waste tile content, respectively. This suggests that the higher waste tile content leads to denser soil packing due to particle agglomeration.
3. Optimum Moisture Content (OMC): An increase in OMC was observed across all waste tile percentages, indicating that higher amounts of waste tiles require more moisture for optimal compaction.
4. The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) value of the black cotton soil showed significant improvement with the incorporation of waste tiles, highlighting the positive effect of waste tiles in enhancing the soil's strength and stability.

6.0 Recommendations

1. Optimization of Waste Tile Proportions: Although the current study demonstrated that the incorporation of waste tiles enhances brick strength, further research should explore the use of higher percentages of waste tiles. This would help determine the optimal proportion for maximizing strength and improving other mechanical properties.
2. Assessment of Heat Resistance: Future studies should investigate the heat resistance of the stabilized bricks. This will provide essential data on their suitability for use in environments with high-temperature exposure or in construction applications that demand thermal stability.
3. Long-Term Durability and Water Absorption: It is recommended that further research be conducted to evaluate the long-term effects of increasing waste tile content on the water absorption and overall durability of the stabilized black cotton soil bricks. This will help assess the sustainability of these bricks, particularly in regions with high moisture exposure.

REFERENCES

- Adeniji, F. A. (1991) "Recharge function of vertisolic vadose Zone in sub-sahelian Chad Basin". *Proc. 1st Inter. Conf. On Arid Zone Ideology Hydrology and Water Resources*, Maduguri, pp. 331 – 348
- Alvarez D. B. M & Limoin T. G (1994) *Restauracion de Edificion monumentales, studio de materails y tecnicas instrumentals*. Centro de studios y ezperimentacion de obraspublical, Madrid.
- Anand, K. B. G., & Vageesh, H. P. (2017). Effect of Discarded Plastic Waste as Stabilizer on Engineering Properties of Cohesive Soil. *International Journal of Engineering Technology Science and Research*, 4(12), 779 - 786.
- Amin E. R; (2012) "A review on the soil stabilization using low-cost methods" *Journal of applied sciences Research*, V. 8(4): 2193-2196, 2012, ISSN 1819-544X.
- Balogun, L. A. (1991). "Effect of sand and salt additives on some geotechnical properties of lime stabilized Black Cotton Soil". *The Nigeria Engineer*, Vol. 26 No., 15 – 24.

- BS 1377 - 2. (1990). Methods of test for Soils for civil engineering purposes — Classification tests. *British Standards Institution Publication*.
- BS 1377 - 4. (1990). Methods of test for Soils for civil engineering purposes - : Compaction-related tests. *BSI Standards Publication, London*.
- Firoozi, A. A, Taha M. R & Khan T. (2014): “Assessment of Nano-zeolite in soil properties”. *Journal of Basic Applied science V. 8(19): 292-295*.
- Fraaij Y. and Kentgens O. M, (2008) International Scholarly and Scientific Research & Innovation 4(7) 201 Open Science Index, Civil and Environmental Engineering Vol:4, No:7, 2008 waset.org/Publication/5235
- Gerald, A. M., & Shahriar, A. (2000). Influence of soil type on stabilization with cement kiln dust. *Construction and Building Materials, 14 89-97*.
- Huang A. B, (2013) "Effect of rice husk ash on workability and strength of concrete" Faculty of Engineering and Information Sciences - Papers: Part A. 2013
- Jimenez T. S. (2013) “Strength characteristics of concrete utilizing waste materials. *International Journal of Engineering Research ISSN: 2319-6890* (online), 23475013(print) Volume No.4, Issue No.9, pp: 506-509.
- Kapil, P and Ameta, N. K (2016) “Stabilization of fine sand with ceramic tiles waste as admixture in construction of embankment”. *American Journal of Engineering Research (AJER)*. e-ISSN: 2320-0936, Vol. 5, Issue 8. pp. 206-212
- Mansary U. and Ghali R., (2017) “Experimental Study on Partial Replacement FineAggregate By Broken Tiles in Concrete”.
- Medjo .E. & Riskowski, G. (2004). —A procedure for processing mixtures of soil, cement and sugar cane bagasse. *Agricultural Engineering International Journal of Scientific Research and Development Manuscript BC 990, Vol. III, pp. 1-6*.
- Monteiro, S. N, Mauricio C. & Vieira F. (2004): “Influence of Firing Temperature on the Ceremic Properties of Clays from Campos’s dos Goytacazes, Brazil”. *Journal of Applied Clay Science, Vol 27 (3-4), 229-234*
- Naveen P & Antil H. (2016) “Partial Replacement of Coarse aggregate by Crushed Tiles and Fine aggregate by Granite Powder to improve the Concrete Properties” *International Journal on Emerging Technologies 6(1): 144-150(2015) ISSN No. (Print): 0975-8364ISSN No. (Online): 2249-3255*
- Newman, K. and Tingle, J. S., (2004), “Emulsion Polymers for soil stabilization”, 2004 FAA Worldwide Airport Technology Transfert conference, Atlantic city, New Jersey, USA.
- Nigerian General Specifications (1997). Roads and Bridges. Federal Ministry of Works, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Ola, S. A. (1978) —The geology and geotechnical properties of the black cotton soils of North Eastern Nigeria. *Engineering Geology, Vol. 12, pp. 375-391*.
- Osinubi, K. J., Soni, E. J. & Ijimdiya, T. S. (2010) —Lime and slag admixture improvement of tropical black clay road foundation *Transportation Research Board (TRB) 89th Annual Meeting CD-ROM, January 10 - 14 Washington, D. C., U.S.A. Subject:*

Recycled Materials in Transportation Infrastructure, Session AFP40 – Physico-chemical and Biological Processes in Soils Committee, Paper # .10-0585, pp. 1 -18.

Plait, R. M. (1953). “Determination of swelling pressure of black cotton soil–A method.” Proceedings of the Third Int’l. Conference on Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering, Zurich, Switzerland, 16th – 27th August, Vol. 1, pp. 170–172.

Rakhil, K and Devi, K (2016) “Review on the effect of waste ceramic dust on the geotechnical properties of expansive soils”. International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology. Vol. 03, Issue 12, PP 1336 - 1342

Samadi K. & Hussein M. W, (2015) “The durability properties of ceramic industry waste as coarse aggregate in concrete”. International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education.

Sasah J and Kankam C. K (2017): Study of bricks mortar using saw dust as partial replacement for sand. Journal of civil engineering and construction Technology. Vol. 8(6), pp. 59-66, ISSN 2141-2634

Tomlinson, M.J. (1999), Foundation Design and Construction. 6th edition, Longman, Harlow, Essex.

Venkatesh N, Heera L. M and Rakesh J. P, (2018) “Multi-scale laboratory investigation on black cotton soils stabilized with calcium carbide residue and fly ash” Journal of Engg. Research Vol. 6 No. (4) 18 pp 1-15